

Supplementary material S1

Sailer, Utley et al.: Lanes, Clusters, Lines of Sight

Observation protocol

Project Name: Reconfigurable Diagnostic Hubs

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Project Aims: The project is set up to investigate the current practice of eye examinations at Moorfields Eye Hospital with the aim of optimizing the flow of patients in time and space. In addition to their Cayton St site, a new hub in Hoxton was opened in January 2021 to catch up with the Covid-induced patient backlog. Clinicians report that neither site runs optimally, as examinations take longer than expected, yet it is not known where time is lost. Based on observations, space syntax modelling and queueing simulation flow models, the aim of the project is to provide spatial and temporal configurations that are time-efficient and adaptable to different settings.

Aims of the Observations:

The aim of the observations is to study current journeys of glaucoma patients through space with detailed timings of examinations on different stations both in Cayton St and Hoxton. Two types of observation methods – journey observation and zonal observation, will be used to understand patient examination times and 3 trained research assistants (RAs) will be gathering data for a period of 3 days on each site. The collected information will help to identify causes of delays in the examination process which could be spatial, technician-related or patient-related.

Ethics and Risks:

Data will be captured on tablets which will cause no risk to the observers or participants. The RAs will receive NHS honorary research contracts and would be offered a Covid vaccine in order to minimize risks. A full risk assessment on UCL RiskNet has been produced and approved by Christoph Lindner, Dean of the Bartlett on 7/5/21. The research is exempt from NHS ethical approval as it falls under the category of service improvement as confirmed by the Moorfields clinical team.

Risks on Site

Do not take unnecessary valuables and keep tablets / mobile phones stowed away when outside. Bring food and drinks. Make regular breaks.

Sites for observation:

Cayton St: Cayton Street Clinic, Moorfields Eye Hospital, 4-12 Cayton St, London EC1V 2NT

Hoxton: Moorfields at Hoxton, 1&5 Bracklyn Street (Off Eagle Wharf Road), Hoxton, London N1 7TX

Dates of observation:

Hoxton: 23 June – 29 June 2021

Cayton St: 24 June – 6 July 2021

Observation Instructions

1. Cayton St Spatial Layout

The Cayton Clinic has three main zones: waiting area (C-1), room with eight stations (C-3) and another room with seven stations (C-5). Stations are numbered from 1 to 15. There are two corridors (C-2 and C-4) which connect the spaces. The circulation is expected to be one-way in theory, starting from the waiting area (after checking in), proceeding to C-3 through C-2 corridor, then C-5 through C-4 corridor and ending at the waiting area again (following the yellow arrows on the floor plan). Please see the floor plan for more details.

For the zonal observations, each observer will be allocated a zone to observe stations (Zone C-3 and C-5). An observation node on the floor plan indicates the position of the observer during observations for each of the zones. These are the best spots to see all stations in each zone, while not hindering movement or interfering in diagnosis. Observers need to be careful around patients and keep a reasonable and safe distance.

2. Hoxton Spatial Layout

Hoxton has examination stations arranged in three lanes (zones C-3, C-4 and C-5), an entrance zone C-1, a circulation zone C-2 and an exit zone C-6. Entrance and exit are separate, so there should be a relatively clear one-way circulation in place.

For the zonal observations, each observer will be allocated a lane to observe stations (Zone C-3, C-4 and C-5).

3. Types of Observations

There are two main types of observations conducted in this research.

Journey observations:

In this type of observation, the observer follows a patient throughout their journey from the check-in point, proceeding to the waiting area, moving from one station to another, reporting for check out and then leaving the premise. Of interest is how long each patient spends at a station and how long and where they spend waiting in-between stations. On a typical visit to the clinic, a patient has four consultations that take place at four different stations. This type of observation is meant to be also qualitative so please take as many notes as possible.

An example of the observation spreadsheet for this type of observation is shown below. Each line in the excel sheet of the journey observation represents what happens at one

step of the process. The observer starts a new line whenever the patient moves from one step to another. Section 4 provides a definition of each data entry column.

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J
1	Day	Shift	Patient ID	Location	Activity	Technician ID	Start time	End time	Patient English	Notes
2	1	AM	55	5	exam	JoSm	09:13:07	09:28:12	fluent	swift examination
3	1									
4	1									
5	1									
6	1									
7	1									
8	1									

Zonal Observation:

In this type of observation, the observer stands at one of the observer nodes indicated on the floor plan to observe all stations within the designated zone. Of interest is how long a patient spends at each station. All stations within the boundary of the zone must be observed simultaneously, with no need to go outside and see what happens before or after.

An example of the observation spreadsheet for this type of observation is shown below. Each line in the excel sheet represents one step of the process at a single station per observed patient. The observer starts a new line for every different process a patient undergoes at a station or the same patient at a different station. Section 4 provides a definition of each data entry column.

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J
1	Day	Shift	Patient ID	Location	Activity	Technician ID	Start time	End time	Patient English	Notes
2	1	AM	55	5	exam	JoSm	09:13:07	09:28:12	fluent	swift examination
3	1									
4	1									
5	1									
6	1									
7	1									
8	1									

What is a process?

The full glaucoma examination consists of four consecutive steps:

- 1) Pressure and vision (on a machine called ORA)
- 2) Measure eyesight (in Hoxton: on a separate station with a machine called Autorefractor; in Cayton Street on a mobile handheld device called viscometer, normally undertaken before step 3, but already at station 3)
- 3) visual field test (on a machine called HFA)
- 4) imaging (on a machine called OCT)

A process in the way we want to capture them in the observations is an eye examination step undertaken at one of the above-mentioned machines / stations. Transition times between stations, or between waiting area and stations are only captured in the full journey observations, but not during the majority of the zonal observations.

4. Definition of data entry in the observation sheets

Day

There are ten days of observations in total (1-10). This is constant and does not change on each sheet. The observer will be provided with different sheets for each day of observations.

Shift

There are three clinic periods during the day in Cayton Street: Morning (AM), Afternoon (PM) and Evening (EVE) and two in Hoxton (AM / PM). The observed needs to choose this value from the dropdown menu, based on which clinic period they are covering.

Patient ID

Every patient who enters the clinic for examination will be given a sticker by the receptionist with a ref number from 1 to 72 (which is the maximum number of patients per day in Cayton, the maximum number of patients per day in Hoxton is 50). Each observer needs to write down this number for each data entry. If a patient does not have a number, the observer needs to ask the receptionist to provide the patient with a number or ask the technician who accompanies the patient to help.

Location

Each station has a station ID displayed on the table. This value should be entered from the drop-down options. If the table does not have a label, please check the excel sheet tab 'check plan' which has the number of stations on the floor plan. Note: the stations in Cayton are numbered clockwise, starting from the observer's left-hand side if they are standing in their observer node (back against the wall). Hoxton stations are numbered linearly by lane.

For the journey observations corridors, toilets, waiting areas etc. are available from the drop-down menu.

Activity

For zonal observations, activity=exam in Hoxton, as we classify the whole length of the time that a patient sits on the chair of an examination station as 'exam'.

In Cayton Street, when patients approach station 3-6 or 11-14 (HFA), typically two processes will occur, one after the other, first the eyesight measurement (mobile device, called viscometer), then the field test (large machine). This means activity can either be 'exam' or 'exam visco'.

For journey observations, a larger number of activities are available from the drop-down menu, including check in, exam, wait_sit, wait_stand, talk to someone and other (toilet for example). The focus of all activity observations is the patient. Note: we do not capture walking as an activity, as we assume patients will be walking / be in transit from one process observed to another, so the difference in end time of one process and the start time of the next process will automatically be assumed to be walking. Therefore, if the patients are not walking, use another activity to capture what they are doing.

Technician ID

This is the ID of the technician accompanying each patient. Each observer needs to enter the first two letters of the technician's first name and the first two letters of their last name. Each technician has a name tag which is visible on their clothing. For example, a technician with the name 'Kerstin Sailer' will get an ID 'KeSa'.

Start time

This is the start of each process you are recording. As accurately as possible, note the time when the patient has sat down. This is not necessarily the time a patient comes near the station. The observer needs to use the formula '=now()' which will automatically generate the current time in the form of hour/minutes/seconds. Observers need to be very careful around this column and try to enter the data once and proceed to next columns. Each observer needs to take continuous screenshots of the recorded data during observations (as data backup). We recommend every half an hour. You could set up a reminder on your phone but please don't use sound as this may disturb people around, just a buzz.

End time

This is the end of each process/examination you are recording. Again, try to accurately capture when the examination is finished. This is the moment in which the patient leaves the seat. Do not include transition times or waiting times (standing) in the times recorded for the examination process. The observer needs to use the same formula '=now()' to enter the value.

Patient English

The observer needs to assess and record the fluency in English of each patient. Each observer can choose from four levels in the drop-down menu: 'fluent', 'few issues', 'many issues', 'translator'. For this, the observer should try to be attentive and overhear the dialogues that take place.

Notes

Please use this field to note anything you feel is worth recording. This could include notes on occurring delays, causes for waiting, etc. It could also include notes on the technician, e.g. when they have to leave the stations temporarily, etc.

5. Observation Schedule

Each observer will receive their own observation schedule. The schedules have to work around several constraints, i.e. Hoxton does not always have all three lanes open and Cayton Street has three shifts rather than two and on some half days they share their space with Urgent Care, hence we're avoiding those time slots.

Observers have to stick to their own schedule in order to cover the number of observations we need.

Times for journey observations are generally allocated at the start of observations, so that observers can familiarize themselves with the flow of the examinations. Breaks are scheduled regularly – they are indicative. Observers should aim to finish a set of observations before going on break. When break time is approaching during zonal observations, no new processes should be started, but all existing should be completed.

Note: each patient observation journey should take approximately 30-45min, so it is suggested to complete as many as possible in the allocated time slots.

6. Data Backup

Observers should log into the NHS Guest Wifi upon first arrival at the clinic and make sure the tablets are connected to the internet throughout.

Excel sheets save automatically on the tablets. Observers need to log into their Microsoft 365 account at the beginning (once) in order to edit and save data. Use 'save as' at the start of the day initially and choose your OneDrive as file location. This should save the file onto the cloud. Every evening when you get home, please locate the file in your cloud and email it to the project PI.

For an additional backup, please make screenshots regularly – this is particularly important for the time capture.

The Excel sheets have been programmed to not update cells automatically (important so that times are not updated every time a new start / end time is entered). Do not change anything in the settings / options.

7. General Rules of Observations

- Always wear your honorary researcher badge and a facial mask.
- Try to be discrete but attentive and record every required field of information.

- If you feel that you messed up a data entry, especially when it comes to timings and station IDs, please indicate this in the notes.
- The observer node is an initial suggestion. Please feel free to move discreetly to other spots which will facilitate your observations. However, be careful to not stay on the path of patients and staff or invade patient's privacy.